

ISic3357

I.Sicily inscription 3357

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object

stele

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

2006.07.25; 2013.09.30 (Prag)

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

necropolis of contrada Canalicchio (gift to museum)

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 15290

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [N]ικοδάμ[ου]

Apparatus

text from autopsy (Prag)

Translation (en)

(Tomb) of Nikodamos

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 644862

EDCS 70900961

Bibliography

Orsi, P. 1900. Frammenti epigrafici sicelioti. *Rivista di storia antica*. 5: 39-66. At 61 no.40 dr

Libertini, G 1929. Il regio museo archeologico di Siracusa. *Guide dei musei italiani*. Roma. At 124

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-18): ISic3357. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4358430>

15290.

Photo J. Prag, Aut. Assessorato Beni Culturali Regione Siciliana n.10681 del
06/05/2014